

REVIEWED INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL

***Electronic International
Interdisciplinary
Research Journal (EIJR)***

ISSN: 2277-8721)

Impact factor (IIFS): 0.987

Bi-Monthly

VOL - III

ISSUES - V

Sep -Oct

[2014]

**Chief-
Editor:**

**U b a l e
A m o l
B a b a n**

[**Editorial/Head Office:** 108, Gokuldham Society, Dr.Ambedkar chowk, Near TV Towar,Badlapur, MS ,

Contact Off : 09822307164

**TO STUDY THE EFFECTIVENESS OF INITIATORY SCHOOL
EXPERIENCES ON STUDENT TEACHER**

Education

Dr.Naik Tarsing B.

Assistant Professor

S.M.T .Govt. College of Education, Kolhapur.

Abstract:

This study sought to identify the effectiveness of initiatory school experiences on student's teacher. In initiatory school experiences student teacher using communication, observation interaction techniques .In the initiatory school experiences student teacher develop the knowledge and information. The student teacher don't have the basic knowledge of the pupil psychology, student teacher observe the basic urges which stimulate pupil behavior and develop his the trait of leadership. In this programme student teacher supervise all the activities carried out in the school. This research paper examines the accountability and effectiveness of initiatory school experiences on student teacher.

Keywords: *Initiatory experiences, Interaction, Techniques, Participation, school, observation.*

Introduction:

Traditional education meant formal learning carried on extensively inside the classroom. Every experience in life ,every activity from the cradle to the grave, is regarded as education. Book learning is no longer considered the whole education and an earnest attempt is being made to secure desirable gains from other forms of training. The National Curriculum Framework (NCF) 2005 places different demands and expectations on the teacher, which need to be addressed both by initial and continuing teacher education. The importance of competent teachers to the nation's school system can in no way be overemphasized. It is well known that

the quality and extent of learner achievement are determined primarily by teacher competence, sensitivity and teacher motivation. It is common knowledge too that the academic and professional standards of teachers constitute a critical component of the essential learning conditions for achieving the educational goals.

The student teacher acquires complete, accurate, direct and first-hand information. The initiatory school experience link between the profession and real life.

W.M. Gregory “,Education has been too far removed from the basic experiences of modern life .Many schools are quite deficient in opportunities for sense perception ,exploration and raw experiences. They need fewer words and more activities, with things, situation, conditions and relations. For useful learning, pupils require experiences with the raw material of life, a garden, a shop, a live animal collection, a trip of a farm, a mill , a store , a park, a museum all must have a place in the modern school. The initiatory school experience as a matter of fact,is the most real and most concrete of the usual techniques and it is the most accessible and often the least expensive.

Initiatory school experiences

The student teacher observe the school teacher as the main source and dispenser of information in the classroom. Student teachers understand and observe the information given about the subject matter. Initiatory school experiences strategy allow student teacher to develop skills, abilities, process and attitudes required for critical thinking. Student teacher directly observe the teaching-learning process is challenging and A lively teacher uses humors which is a valuable teaching tool for establishing a conducive classroom climate. It improves instructional

effectiveness and is fundamental to positive classroom learning. Student understand the classroom needs effort, skill and tact on the part of the teacher. Student teacher observe of problems such as unconducive environment for proper academic work, insufficient classroom blocks; these problems make it impossible for teachers to perform their duties effectively. Although, many factors determine the success or failure in the classroom, to a large extent, the teacher determines the social environment in the classroom. Through initiatory school experience the student teacher understand the relationship between the school teacher and the student.

Objective:

- 1.To provide the professional attitudes of student teacher .
- 2.To make them conscious of teacher responsibility.
- 3.To acquire knowledge and understanding of school campus.
- 4.To know the function and contribution of human resources in the school.
- 5.To develop the attitude and ideas for school surrounding adjustment.
- 6.To help students teacher to define the factor affecting on school campus.
- 7.To appraise the work of the human resources in the school.

Significance of the Study :

Initiatory school experience will help the student teacher to acquire the knowledge and information of school campus, school administrators plan towards positive education .It have clear high social and intellectual values as clear, logical and vigorous thinking is required in the school and develop courage, presence of mind, school teachers activity. Also to recognize the essentially worthwhile that are taking place in the school system, to overcome the inefficiencies of others without losing their good will.

Scope of the Study :

This study covers R.K.Walawalkar highschool all students, teachers, headmaster, superwiser and employee. Also the eleven student teacher of S.M.T. Government college of Education who taking the initiatory school experience state both male and female teachers .

Research Method:

This study researcher adopted survey method appropriate to achieve the objective. Data was collected on interactions in school human resources and to observe the nature of the school campus. In this survey study, the student- teachers, school teacher and students in the R.K. Walawalkar High school in Kolhapur were taught the rudiments of a school campus and activity observation technique. In the classroom Interaction between student and teacher, school physical resources, school human resources.

Area of study :

This was conducted in R.K.Walawalkar High school in Kolhapur state of Maharashtra out of Out of Seven Schools in Kolhapur One Secondary School were used for the study.

Sample and sampling techniques:

The sample of the study consisted of twelve 11 student teachers and 523 students ,one headmaster,23 teachers of R.K.walawalkar Highschool, Kolhapur randomly selected . Eight teachers taught using Interaction , two student-teachers taught using teacher Initiation, students response and teacher evaluation , while two teachers taught using teaching cycles respectively. And other student-teachers observe and collect the information about school physical and human resource. The teachers were experienced and taught each class once.

Procedure for data collection:

The data was collected during Initiatory School Experiences of student-teacher . Before the observation, the researcher made visitation to the R.K. Walawalkar high school, Kolhapur. The researcher concluded by observing each of the student- teacher four working days.An interaction with experienced teachers who working in the school.

Method of data analysis :

The data collected in this study were analyzed as follows: the research question was analyzed using pie charts expressed in gain and gain percentages. The hypothesis was tested using chi square statistics.

Table showing student-teacher interaction with Human resources in the school.

Interaction with human resources		χ^2
----------------------------------	--	----------

Headmaster	Super wiser	Teacher	Office Employee	Total	Calculated
Fo 8 Fe(6.20)	6 (6.82)	12 (12.96)	4 (4.96)	22	2.13
Fo 2 Fe(3.79)	5 (4.17)	4 (3.03)	5 (5.96)	14	
10	11	16	09	46	

Graph 1 showing student-teacher interaction with Human resources in the school

The initiatory school experience to establish an ongoing, systematic mechanism for observation, reviewing, and improving programs. The school surrounding, strength of the school procedures for evaluation outcomes will be measured; what results will be reported, to whom; and how results have been implemented. The maximum teachers were interact with their students, the result obtained after data analysis showed that student-teacher information and observation skills and level of school physical and human resources participation in the process of school working process. The extent of collaboration among student-teacher how focused, lesson and decisions of headmasters. The study therefore challenges student-teacher to engage all students positively in school system.

Conclusion and Suggestions:

In conclusion, our charge was to examine initiatory school experience. Some school have good amenities for the students such as common room, sanitary convenience, provision for mid-day meals and refreshments to be taken and in the case of girl student retiring rooms with necessary conveniences separately. There is equally good work being conducted on the nature of Teaching and learning . A secondary school must have a big hall can assemble a time. Student-Teacher create a warm and lively classroom environment. Student-Teacher should use good question strategies and possibly use modern communication gadgets to reach students. This is necessary so as to draw out knowledge from students that are reflective. The initiatory school experiences helps the student-teacher to make valuable future professional of teacher.

References:

- Brown, Johnes, Lewis, Richard, B. Harcleroad, Fred N. : (1983), "Instructional Technology Media and Methods" New York; Mac Graw Hill Book Co.
- Bruce Joyce,: (1997), Models of Teaching, 5th Edition.
- Buch, M.B. : (1983), "Fourth Survey of Research in Education "New Delhi; National Council of Educational Research and Training.
- Buch, M.B. : (1992) , "Fifth Survey of Research in Education, "New Delhi; National Council of Educational Research and Training.
- Carter, V. Good.: (2006), "How to Do Research in Education", New Delhi; Cosmo Publication.
- Nwangwu, S. (2010) EOCDF: Promoting Education in Rivers State...builds school admin. Block PPSB Bulletin,vol1 no 2.
- Weimer,M (2005) Putting Participation Puzzle together. www.facultyfocus.com. Magna Publications.
- Egbochuku E. O. (2008) Assessment of the Quality of Guidance and Counseling Services to Students' Adjustment in Secondary Schools in Edo State of Nigeria. Research Journal of International Studies Issue 8 (November, 2008)
- Mehta,D ,(2009), "Educational Administration" ,New Delhi;A.P.H.Publicaiton.